

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Effect of simulated rain on head rice yields of varieties under delayed harvest

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Rain can cause harvest delays and losses in rice milling quality. Cycles of high and low moisture can increase the proportion of broken grains during milling.

To test the effect of continuous evening rain on the milling yield of rice, we stagger-planted 20 varieties to obtain simultaneous maturity in Palmira, Colombia, during 9 May-30 Oct 1986. Each variety was transplanted in plots of 9 rows, 10 m long and 30 cm apart. At maturity (20-25% moisture content), each plot was divided in half with a plastic curtain extending from ground level to 30 cm above the top panicle. Simulated rain was applied to one-half of the plots with an atomizer operated at a water pressure of 2 atmospheres, delivering 60 liters/h and covering a diameter of 1.5 m. A timing clock regulated the daily application of moisture from 1800 to 0600 h for 3 wk.

Both conditions were sampled each week. Samples were taken at 1100 h, regardless of environmental conditions. Grain moisture measurements at harvest indicated that misting resulted in mean values 2.5% higher (20.9 vs 18.4%) after the first week and 1.1% higher (13.0 vs 11.9%) after the second week. Misting had no significant effect on grain moisture content at harvest with a delay of 3 wk. Rough rice samples of 125 g were dried and milled using standard McGill laboratory equipment.

Head rice yield slopes for each treatment within each variety were calculated (see table). Seven varieties showed similar slopes under simulated rain and control conditions, whereas the rest showed faster head rice reduction

Head rice yield slopes of varieties under 3 wk of delayed harvesting and the application of simulated rain.

Variety	Country of origin	Treatment ^a	Regression equation ^b			
			<i>b</i> ₀	<i>b</i> ₁	<i>b</i> ₂	<i>t</i> ^c
BR IRGA 409	Brazil	SR	58.2	-0.432	0.010	3.42*
		C	51.4	1.635	-0.074	
BR IRGA 410	Brazil	SR	46.7	-1.575	0.015	0.84 ns
		C	53.9	-1.251	0.012	
Ceysvoni	Surinam	SR	20.8	-1.847	0.059	0.26 ns
		C	20.2	-1.265	0.034	
CICA4	Colombia	SR	39.2	-1.768	0.073	9.56**
		C	36.5	1.732	-0.087	
CICA7	Colombia	SR	36.1	-2.569	0.080	0.88 ns
		C	37.6	-1.541	0.031	
CICA8	Colombia	SR	53.6	-1.455	-0.029	5.36**
		C	52.7	-0.133	-0.055	
Diwani	Surinam	SR	16.4	0.886	-0.057	4.33**
		C	29.6	-0.668	-0.013	
EMPASC 104	Brazil	SR	42.2	-0.755	-0.018	7.15**
		C	47.1	2.173	-0.158	
INIAP7	Ecuador	SR	65.5	-4.310	0.080	5.45**
		C	53.2	-1.507	0.024	
INIAP415	Ecuador	SR	61.9	-5.795	0.211	4.70**
		C	59.3	-4.439	0.179	
INTI	Peru	SR	58.1	0.083	-0.109	1.75 ns
		C	65.0	-0.016	-0.088	
IR36	Philippines	SR	35.8	-3.732	0.109	1.56 ns
		C	31.7	-2.323	0.051	
IR46	Philippines	SR	40.4	-5.312	0.168	3.56*
		C	32.7	-3.228	0.084	
IR52	Philippines	SR	27.9	-3.599	0.122	4.61**
		C	22.4	-1.258	0.029	
IR56	Philippines	SR	48.0	-4.587	0.125	4.42**
		C	44.3	-2.183	0.019	
IR60	Philippines	SR	46.1	-2.345	0.027	3.68*
		C	49.3	-0.595	-0.067	
Metica 1	Colombia	SR	42.5	-1.234	0.006	3.15*
		C	46.3	0.280	-0.078	
Oryzica 1	Colombia	SR	60.3	-4.057	0.087	6.60**
		C	56.2	-1.476	0.007	
Oryzica 2	Colombia	SR	53.8	-5.419	0.142	2.45 ns
		C	51.6	-3.643	0.061	
Sinaloa A80	Mexico	SR	47.0	1.435	-0.124	0.02 ns
		C	53.3	1.502	-0.125	

^aSR = simulated rain, 15 min every hour from 1800 to 0600 h, C = control. ^b $Y = b_0 + b_1t + b_2t^2$, $R = 0.95$. ^c $H_0: \beta_{1SR} = \beta_{1c}$
 $\beta_{2SR} = \beta_{2c}$

ns, *, ** = nonsignificant and significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels, respectively.

when simulated rain was applied. Within the first group, varieties INTI from Peru and Sinaloa A80 from Mexico seem to have acceptable initial milling yields and a slow rate of quality loss, which suggests a certain degree of tolerance for delayed harvest. Within the group of varieties with faster rate of loss with simulated rain, BR IRGA 409

could also be classified as tolerant; such varieties could be useful in areas where delayed harvest is common and milling quality is demanded. Varieties Oryzica 2 and INIAP415 represent genotypes with acceptable milling yields when harvested on time, but would be discarded if milling evaluations included samples harvested 10-15 d after maturity. □